

MAPA: THE DEVELOPED MICROLEARNING-BASED MODULE IN ARLING PANLIPUNAN 8

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to develop and validate a *microlearning-based module* in *Arling Panlipunan 8*. It employed a quantitative research approach specifically utilizing a design and development study through pretest and posttest. Data were collected forty Grade 8 students in the San Cristobal National High School and fifteen head/master teachers in public institutions using a purposive sampling technique. The study utilized an adopted and modified version of ready-made questionnaires with a content validity index of 1.00. A Paired Sample T-test was used to determine the significant difference between the pretest and posttest, while the mean, Likert Scale, and standard deviation were used to identify the validity and acceptability of the microlearning-based module. Moreover, it was revealed that the content validity level of the microlearning-based module was Highly Valid in terms of objectives ($\bar{x}=3.84$, $SD=0.27$), directions ($\bar{x}=3.87$, $SD=0.27$), topics ($\bar{x}=3.80$, $SD=0.30$), practical exercises ($\bar{x}=3.77$, $SD=0.35$), and clarity ($\bar{x}=3.87$, $SD=0.28$). In addition, the acceptability level of the microlearning-based module was Very Acceptable in terms of usefulness ($\bar{x}=3.77$, $SD=0.35$), presentation ($\bar{x}=3.85$, $SD=0.30$), and suitability ($\bar{x}=3.76$, $SD=0.39$). Furthermore, it was revealed that the students did not meet expectations ($\bar{x}=72.50$, $SD=7.94$) in the pretest, and the posttest result revealed Very Satisfactory with an average of 87.95 and a standard deviation of 6.89. The results revealed there was a significant difference between the pretest and the posttest with a t value of -15.873 ($SD=6.16$, $\bar{x}=-15.45$). Therefore, the developed microlearning-based module was proposed to enhance student engagement and comprehension by delivering concise, focused learning segments tailored to their cognitive load and attention span, allowing students to absorb essential concepts efficiently without feeling overwhelmed by excessive information.

Keywords: *MAPA, Development and Validation of Microlearning-based Module in Araling Panlipunan*

INTRODUCTION

As the education sectors all around the world progress towards recovery from the pandemic-induced period of distance learning, the transition back to in-person instruction presents persistent educational challenges that require resolution. Although numerous challenges exist, they ultimately impact a fundamental objective of education: student learning, as evidenced by their academic success.

World Bank (2021) indicated that seven out of ten junior high school students were still impacted by societal conditions such as war, riots, natural disasters, and other contemporary events that necessitated their return to remote learning. Hence, despite being promoted to intermediate levels, learners lacked the foundation necessary for their current grade level. Furthermore, longer lesson formats hindered student learning, as foundational skills had to be focused on first, necessitating simplicity without sacrificing the intended learning objectives.

In the Philippine context, the Asian Disaster Reduction Center (ADRC, 2024) reported that natural disasters were among the reasons why the Department of Education pivoted to modular distance learning from time to time. As a result, teaching vital skills like academic performance and attention span became a significant challenge. As students became more reliant on the internet and social media, it was observed in the academic community that their attention spans were getting shorter. Additionally, this exacerbated the situation on students' academic performance.

Likewise, teachers at public junior high schools throughout the Philippines, both urban and rural, encountered many instructional problems. In Araling Panlipunan 8, which focuses on World History, students frequently experienced difficulties comprehending intricate concepts within constrained learning periods (Hidayat, 2022). Classroom observations and informal interactions with educators indicated that students frequently disengaged during prolonged lectures and complex readings. Educators, despite their readiness to innovate, were deprived of excellent materials that corresponded with the curriculum and students' digital behaviors.

To address these dilemmas, DepEd implemented the Basic Education Development Plan (BEDP) 2030, where projects and programs targeting educational issues were supposed to be already established. However, the schools in Region IV-A CALABARZON only experienced the aforementioned through the reinforcement of fundamental skills, or "back to basics," which was incorporated by teachers in the Learning Packets (LEAPs) that adhered to the PIVOT IV-A learning modules and the most essential learning competencies (MELCs).

Despite this, learning areas such as the MAKABAYAN subjects were neglected as the focus was only on academic ones. One of the issues was that answering the recommended long modular activities became difficult and lowered student motivation, despite the fact that they were willing to study. As a result, students who had a short

attention span scored poorly academically in learning areas. These were reflected as well in the micro setting of public high schools.

In the context of San Cristobal National High School in the Division of Calamba City, the Mean Percentage Score of the Quarterly Examinations in Araling Panlipunan 8, which emphasized World History in the previous school year, 2023-2024, yielded that Grade 10 learners only attained 66.30%, the Grade 9 learners achieved 62.40%, the Grade 7 learners obtained 56.38%, and the Grade 8 learners recorded the lowest score of 50.59%. It was notable that all Junior High School levels were not able to attain the passing rate of 75%. Hence, the students, specifically the Grade 8 learners, needed further scaffolding in their academic learning in the said learning area.

Furthermore, although students frequently utilized mobile technology and social media, these resources were seldom incorporated into formal education in a pedagogically effective way. The disparity between pupils' daily internet activities and classroom instruction signified a lost opportunity. Philippine schools required instructional resources that were curriculum-aligned, pedagogically robust, and attuned to students' learning preferences and realities.

This study, grounded in DepEd Memorandum 024, s. 2022, which mandated the implementation of the Basic Education Development Plan (BEDP) 2030, aimed to develop and evaluate the viability and efficacy of a Microlearning-Based Module in Araling Panlipunan 8. This researcher-made learning module employed bite-sized learning tailored to the attention span and cognitive load of contemporary Filipino learners, structured in the Introduction, Development, Engagement, and Assimilation (I.D.E.A.) format. This module sought to enhance students' academic performance in Araling Panlipunan, a MAKABAYAN subject with no existing national program, while additionally developing comprehensive learning materials that effectively engaged students' attention in World History.

Research Objectives

This study developed and validated a Microlearning Module in Araling Panlipunan 8. Specifically, it attained the following objectives:

1. Design a microlearning-based module in *Araling Panlipunan 8* based and aligned with the K to 12 Curriculum MELCs.
 2. Establish the content validity and acceptability of the developed microlearning-based module in *Araling Panlipunan 8*.
 3. Determine the pretest and posttest results of the Grade 8 student participants upon utilizing the developed microlearning-based module in *Araling Panlipunan 8*.
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METHODOLOGY

This study utilized the Design and Development Research (DDR) method. The objective of the Design and Development Research Method was to build an empirical

foundation for the creation of instructional products and resources, as well as new or improved models that governed their development. The development and validation of the microlearning-based module were conducted in the Division of Calamba City, while its pilot testing was solely conducted in San Cristobal National High School with 40 Grade 8 learners in the School Year 2024-2025. The study utilized the Design and Development Research (DDR) and the ADDIE Framework. Hence, its development required two sets of respondents, both were chosen using the non-probability sampling method, specifically the purposive sampling technique. This study required two sets of respondents—one set in the validation process and another in the pilot testing of the microlearning-based module. They were both chosen purposively.

For the validation process of the microlearning-based module in Araling Panlipunan 8, a total of 15 interraters were needed to validate its content and validity. These interraters were composed of master and head teachers of Social Studies in the Division of Calamba City, as they were deemed experts in teaching Araling Panlipunan. To gather the pertinent data for its conduct, this study utilized four research instruments. These were the pretest, the developed Microlearning-Based Module in Araling Panlipunan 8, the posttest, and the validation tool for the assessment of the developed learning module. The aforementioned research instruments had required validation before their administration and implementation. For the pretest and posttest, which had been parallel summative tests, they had been checked and validated based on the Table of Specifications (TOS) in the last two weeks of the third quarter and the first two weeks of the fourth quarter of Araling Panlipunan 8 by the Research Director, Statistician, Thesis Adviser, School of Graduate Studies Professor, and the School Head of San Cristobal National High School. For this study to have been properly executed, it was essential to implement a series of preliminary actions and procedural steps for data gathering. These steps ensured that the execution of the inquiry was conducted with attention to the research protocols and the personnel involved. Utmost caution had been exercised, and prior agreement had been secured from all respondents regarding the ethical issues of the data-gathering method in the study. This had entailed obtaining consent from pertinent personnel, including Araling Panlipunan teachers, master and head teachers, students, the School Head, and Division Authorities.

The data collected were interpreted utilizing the following statistical tools in line with the purpose statements of this study. Frequency, percentage, Likert Scale, Average, and Standard Deviation were used to measure or quantify the level of acceptability and validity of the developed microlearning-based module based on the responses of the evaluators in the four-point Likert Scale evaluation tool in terms of Objectives, Directions, Topics, Practical Exercises, Clarity, Usefulness, Presentation, and Suitability. T-test was used for the test of significance of the pretest and posttest results to determine whether there a statistically significant difference between them in the microlearning-based module in Araling Panlipunan 8.

RESULTS

Table 1.1

List of Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs), Learning Objectives, and Course Topics in the Microlearning-based Module

Lesson	MELCs	Learning Objectives	Topics
1	Naipapapaliwanag ang kaugnayan ng Rebolusyong Pangkaisipan sa Rebolusyong Amerikano at Pranses.	Maipaliwanag ang kaugnayan ng Rebolusyong Pangkaisipan sa Rebolusyong Amerikano at Pranses.	Kaugnayan ng Rebolusyong Pangkaisipan sa Rebolusyong Amerikano at Pranses
2	Nasusuri ang dahilan, pangyayari at epekto ng Ikalawang Yugto ng Kolonyalismo (Imperyalismo)	Masuri ang dahilan, pangyayari at epekto ng Ikalawang Yugto ng Kolonyalismo (Imperyalismo)	Ikalawang Yugto ng Kolonyalismo (Imperyalismo)
3	Nasusuri ang mga dahilan, mahahalagang pangyayaring naganap, at bunga ng Unang Digmaang Pandaigdig.	Masuri ang mga dahilan, mahahalagang pangyayaring naganap, at bunga ng Unang Digmaang Pandaigdig.	Ang Unang Digmaang Pandaigdig
4	Nasusuri ang mga dahilan, mahahalagang pangyayaring naganap, at bunga ng Ikalawang Digmaang Pandaigdig.	Masuri ang mga dahilan, mahahalagang pangyayaring naganap, at bunga ng Ikalawang Digmaang Pandaigdig.	Ang Ikalawang Digmaang Pandaigdig

Table 1.2

Components of the Microlearning-based Module in Araling Panlipunan 8 (Microlearning: Agapay sa Pagkatuto sa Araling Panlipunan 8 (M.A.P.A.))

Component	Description
<i>Panimula</i> (Introduction)	The first component of the microlearning-based module aims to engage students' pre-existing knowledge, stimulate their interest, and/or offer a concise summary of the lesson's content. This section links the subject matter to real-life experiences or prior lessons through motivational exercises, drills and drills, explicitly articulating the learning objectives to provide students with direction and purpose.

<i>Pagpapaunlad</i> (Development)	The second component is where the concise version of the core content is conveyed through bite-size learning. This section provides a comprehensive yet short elucidation of the subject, encompassing definitions, fundamental concepts, and pertinent instances.
<i>Pakikipagpalihan</i> (Engagement)	The third component emphasizes active learning through engaging activities that students can immerse themselves in to check their learning. At this stage, students are urged to engage in activities that foster critical thinking, teamwork, and self-reflection.
<i>Paglalapad</i> (Assimilation)	The fourth component enables learning to assimilate and individualize their learning experience through performance tasks. Here, they contemplate the instruction, articulate their comprehension, and assimilate the knowledge into their cognitive framework. Assimilation facilitates the comprehension and retention of knowledge for future application, rather than mere memorization.

Table 2.1.1

Content Validity of the Microlearning-based Module in Araling Panlipunan 8 in terms of Objectives

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. Relevant to the topics in <i>Araling Panlipunan 8</i>	3.93	HV
2. Specific and clearly stated	3.73	HV
3. Measurable, attainable, and result-oriented	3.93	HV
4. Well-planned, formulated, and organized	3.80	HV
5. Time-bound	3.80	HV
General Assessment	3.84	HV
Standard Deviation	0.27	

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV) 1.75-2.49 Slightly Valid (SV)
2.50-3.24 Valid (V) 1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Table 2.1.2

Content Validity of the Microlearning-based Module in Araling Panlipunan 8 in terms of Direction

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. Simple and clear	3.93	HV
2. Easy to follow	3.80	HV

3. Properly sequenced	3.87	HV
4. Can be done independently	3.87	HV
General Assessment	3.87	HV
Standard Deviation	0.27	
Legend:	3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV)	1.75-2.49 Slightly Valid (SV)
	2.50-3.24 Valid (V)	1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Table 2.1.3

Content Validity of the Microlearning-based Module in Araling Panlipunan 8 in terms of Topics

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. Are sequenced according to curriculum	3.73	HV
2. Are logically presented	3.80	HV
3. Address the learners' needs	3.80	HV
4. Are equipped with background and concepts	3.87	HV
5. Are easily understood by the learners	3.80	HV
General Assessment	3.80	HV
Standard Deviation	0.30	
Legend:	3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV)	1.75-2.49 Slightly Valid (SV)
	2.50-3.24 Valid (V)	1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Table 2.1.4

Content Validity of the Microlearning-based Module in Araling Panlipunan 8 in terms of Practical Exercises

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. Inconsonance with the objectives	3.87	HV
2. Appropriate to learners' abilities	3.73	HV
3. Adequate to enhance learners' comprehension and reading skills	3.87	HV
4. Sufficient to determine the mastery level of learners	3.73	HV
5. Stimulate higher order thinking skills	3.67	HV
General Assessment	3.77	HV
Standard Deviation	0.35	
Legend:	3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV)	1.75-2.49 Slightly Valid (SV)
	2.50-3.24 Valid (V)	1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Table 2.1.5

Content Validity of the Microlearning-based Module in Araling Panlipunan 8 in terms of Clarity

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. Information is clear and simple	3.87	HV
2. Language use is clear and easy to understand	3.93	HV
3. The concepts for each activity are re-arranged logically and ensure that there is no duplication	3.93	HV
4. Information suits learners' interest.	3.87	HV
General Assessment	3.87	HV
Standard Deviation	0.28	
Legend:	3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV) 2.50-3.24 Valid (V)	1.75-2.49 Slightly Valid (SV) 1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Table 2.2.1

Level of Acceptability of the Microlearning-based Module in Araling Panlipunan 8 in terms of Usefulness

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. The materials prepares the learners to think logically and critically	3.53	VA
2. The concepts in the material are simple and comprehensible	3.87	VA
3. The material helps the students master the topics at their own pace	3.87	VA
4. The material provides opportunity for the development	3.80	VA
5. The learning content provide adequate information on the topics presented	3.80	VA
6. The material motivates learners to become actively involved in the learning activities	3.73	VA
7. The material stimulates the learners to intellectual activities which help them master the least learned competencies	3.73	VA
8. The activities seek to relate new concepts from previous learning	3.80	VA
General Assessment	3.77	VA
Standard Deviation	0.35	
Legend:	3.25-4.00 Very Acceptable (VA) 2.50-3.24 Acceptable (A)	1.75-2.49 Partially Acceptable (PA) 1.00-1.74 Not Acceptable (NA)

Table 2.2.2

Level of Acceptability of the Microlearning-based Module in Araling Panlipunan 8 in terms of Presentation

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. Topics are presented in logical and sequential order	3.80	VA
2. The direction is concise readable, and easy to follow	3.80	VA
3. The topics fit the learners' needs	3.93	VA
4. The presentation of each lesson is attractive and interesting	3.87	VA
General Assessment	3.85	VA
Standard Deviation	0.30	
Legend:	3.25-4.00 Very Acceptable (VA)	1.75-2.49 Partially Acceptable (PA)
	2.50-3.24 Acceptable (A)	1.00-1.74 Not Acceptable (NA)

Table 2.2.3

Level of Acceptability of the Microlearning-based Module in Araling Panlipunan 8 in terms of Suitability

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. Activities consider the varying attitudes and capabilities	3.73	VA
2. Activities are appropriate to the subject matter	3.80	VA
3. Activities are relevant, interesting, and self-motivating to the learners	3.73	VA
4. Enrichment activities cater the different learning needs of learners	3.67	VA
5. Language of the program is within the vocabulary range of learners	3.87	VA
General Assessment	3.76	VA
Standard Deviation	0.39	
Legend:	3.25-4.00 Very Acceptable (VA)	1.75-2.49 Partially Acceptable (PA)
	2.50-3.24 Acceptable (A)	1.00-1.74 Not Acceptable (NA)

Table 3.1

Pretest Results of the Grade 8 Students upon Utilizing the Developed Microlearning-based Module in Araling Panlipunan 8

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	0	0

Very Satisfactory	1	2.5
Satisfactory	9	22.5
Fairly Satisfactory	8	20.0
Did not meet Expectations	22	55.0
Total	40	100.00
Average	72.50	
Standard Deviation	7.94	
Legend:	90-100 Outstanding	85-89 Very Satisfactory
	80-84 Satisfactory	
	75-79 Fairly Satisfactory	74 below Did not Meet Expectations

Table 3.2

Posttest Results of the Grade 8 Student upon Utilizing the Developed Microlearning-based Module in Araling Panlipunan 8

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	21	52.5
Very Satisfactory	9	22.5
Satisfactory	5	12.5
Fairly Satisfactory	4	10.0
Did not meet Expectations	1	2.5
Total	40	100.00
Average	87.95	
Standard Deviation	6.89	
Legend:	90-100 Outstanding	85-89 Very Satisfactory
	80-84 Satisfactory	75-79 Fairly Satisfactory
	74 below Did not Meet Expectations	

Table 3.3

Test of Significant Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Results of the Grade 8 Students

Indicators	Test	Paired Differences				Remarks	Decision
		Mean	SD	T	P value		
Araling Panlipunan 8	Pre & Post	- 15.45	6.16	-15.873	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

DISCUSSION

This study developed and validated a Microlearning Module in *Araling Panlipunan 8*.

Research Objective 1. Design a Microlearning-based Module in *Araling Panlipunan 8* based and aligned with the K to 12 Curriculum

The developed and validated microlearning-based module in *Araling Panlipunan 8* was a researcher-developed learning module entitled, “Microlearning: *Agapay sa Pagkatuto sa Araling Panlipunan 8* (M.AP.A.) covering four learning competencies in World History. Consequently, the four components of lesson delivery, Introduction, Development, Engagement, and Assessment (I.D.E.A.), were converted into concise knowledge segments and learning activities designed to optimize students' learning potential in Social Studies within a brief timeframe, while maintaining their attention span. The content of the microlearning-based module was derived from the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) prescribed by Department of Education through the PIVOT 4A Budget of Work (BOW). Consequently, the content validity and reliability of the proposed and validated microlearning-based module were checked prior to the reproduction and administration to the learners. These were done by subject experts in the field of teaching *Araling Panlipunan* who are the master teachers and head teachers in the said subject.

The validated microlearning-based module was composed of four Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) with their respective learning objectives, as well as the topics with corresponding activities for the learners to master. The alignment of the learning objectives with the MELCs was keenly followed.

The validated microlearning-based module was specifically and intentionally named as M.A.P.A. (Microlearning: *Agapay sa Pagkatuto sa Araling Panlipunan 8*) as it features a journey-like learning where students were assisted in learning the lesson in bite-sized form, which is the main goal of microlearning. Moreover, familiar characters from pop culture such as Avatar: The Legend of Aang served as the guide of the students for them to learning interactively. Through capitalizing on both the attention span of the learners in bite-sized learning as well as their captivation with pop culture, learning was harnessed to its full potential.

Following the Introduction-Development-Engagement-Assimilation (I.D.E.A.) lesson format, the validated microlearning-based module integrated the concept of microlearning in each of the components while also featuring pop culture themes to captivate the attention of the learners. Since the implementation of the I.D.E.A. lesson format is recommended in teaching *Araling Panlipunan* subjects in the Department of Education, the module encapsulated these four components and retained their essence through bite-sized learning.

In *M.A.P.A.*, the said four lesson components were each guided by a pop culture character from Nickelodeon's Avatar: The Legend of Aang to serve as the more knowledgeable others (MKO) of the learners to guide them in their journey-type learning.

Each of the characters integrated in each lesson was intentionally studied to fit the content of the lesson and the competencies needed to be mastered.

The validated microlearning-based module was firmly grounded in the principles of microlearning, a pedagogical approach designed to enhance knowledge retention and learner engagement through short, focused instructional segments. According to Brew (2023) microlearning-based referred to a method of teaching that involved delivering educational content to students in bite-sized chunks, often lasting between three and five minutes, that were simple to absorb, and at the precise moment when they required it. One of the goals of this approach was to accomplish a focused and clearly articulated educational purpose. Through this, learners had the ability to exercise control over the content and timing of their education, as well as the flexibility to satisfy their educational needs at a time and location that were suitable for them and that could meet their individualized schedules.

Research Objective 2. Establish the content validity and acceptability of the Developed Microlearning-based Module in *Araling Panlipunan 8*.

Objectives were **Highly Valid (3.84)** as to the level of content validity of the developed microlearning-based module in *Araling Panlipunan 8*. This also revealed that all the indicators were **Highly Valid**. Consequently, the indicators “Relevant to the topics in *Araling Panlipunan 8*” and “Measurable, attainable, and result-oriented” yielded the highest mean score of **3.93**, whereas the indicator “Specific and clearly stated” received the lowest mean score of **3.73**. The standard deviation of the assessment was **0.27**, indicating a relatively low variability in the evaluators' responses, which suggests a strong consensus regarding the validity of the module's objectives.

Accordingly, the results indicate that the developed microlearning-based module's objectives manifest relevance to their respective topics, specificity, and clarity. They are also measurable, attainable, result-oriented, well-planned, formulated, organized, and time-bound. Overall, the results imply that the objectives of the microlearning-based module meet the standards.

Learning objectives conveyed the intent of education. When executed effectively, they communicated the expectations that the instructor—and by extension, the academic discipline—held for what students should have comprehended and been capable of after finishing a course of study (Orr et al., 2022). Stapleton-Corcoran (2023), inclined to the results of the study by asserting that learning objectives had to focus on the competencies, knowledge, or demonstrations expected of students, rather than the actions of the instructor. They had needed to decompose the learning task into distinct skill components. Thus, learning objectives had emphasized gradual progress towards a broader educational aim, alongside observable and quantifiable behaviors. This had been accomplished by identifying the precise tasks students had to undertake to attain and exhibit their comprehension of the course material.

Directions was **Highly Valid (3.87)** as to the level of content validity of the developed microlearning-based module in *Araling Panlipunan 8*. This also revealed that all the indicators were **Highly Valid**. In this manner, the indicator “Simple and clear” yielded the highest mean score of **3.93**, while the indicator “Easy to follow” received the lowest

mean score of **3.80**. The standard deviation of **0.27** indicates minimal variability in the evaluators' responses, suggesting a strong consensus regarding the clarity and effectiveness of the module's directions.

Likewise, the results point out that the developed microlearning-based module's directions and instructions are simple, clear, easy to follow, properly sequenced, and can be completed by the learners independently. Ultimately, the results imply that the directions of the microlearning-based module meet the standards.

The City University of New York (2023) emphasized that the directions had to include not only the methods, recommendations, and due dates but also remarks regarding how the content of this module was connected to what the students learned in the past and what they would learn eventually. If required, they had to be written in short phrases and used bullet points and numbered lists. This had been one of the first things that students had seen in the module; yet, it had been best to write it last, as it had been one of the most important elements to be considered for them to understand the tasks.

Similarly, it had been essential for learning modules to include directions that were both clear and succinct, as they served to direct learners, guarantee that they comprehended the material, and encouraged independent learning, which eventually resulted in improved comprehension and the development of skills (De Chavez, 2023). As a result, directions needed to be centered on accomplishing three things: guiding learners and promoting clarity, reinforcing learning and self-development, and improving overall learning experiences.

Topics was Highly Valid (3.80) as to the level of content validity of the developed microlearning-based module in Araling Panlipunan 8. This also revealed that all the indicators were **Highly Valid**. Consequently, the indicator "Are equipped with background and concepts" yielded the highest mean score of **3.87**, whereas the indicator "Are sequenced according to curriculum" received the lowest mean score of **3.73**. The standard deviation of **0.30** indicates minimal variability in the evaluators' responses, suggesting a strong agreement among experts regarding the relevance and sequencing of the module's topics.

Accordingly, the results indicate that the developed microlearning-based module's topics are sequenced based on the requirements of the curriculum, logically presented, address the needs of the learners, are equipped with a conceptual background, and can be easily understood by the students. Overall, the results imply that the topics of the microlearning-based module meet the standards.

Furthermore, a module that was well-structured and contained topics that were carefully selected allowed students to construct a solid foundation of knowledge and abilities in a manner that was both logical and systematic. Learners were encouraged to actively participate in the learning process by engaging with themes that were compelling, which resulted in a greater understanding of the material and increased retention of the information (Lacanihao & Manalastas, 2023).

Practical exercises were Highly Valid (3.77) as to the level of content validity of the developed microlearning-based module in Araling Panlipunan 8. This also revealed that all the indicators were **Highly Valid**. In this manner, the indicators "Inconsonance with

the objectives” and “Adequate to enhance learners' comprehension and reading skills” both yielded the highest mean score of **3.87**, while the indicator “Stimulate higher-order thinking skills” received the lowest mean score of **3.67**. The standard deviation of **0.35** indicates minimal variability in the evaluators' responses, suggesting a strong consensus regarding the effectiveness of the practical exercises.

Likewise, the results point out that the developed microlearning-based module's practical exercises are in parallel with the objectives set forth, appropriate to the needs of the learners, enhance learners' skills in reading, determine the learners' mastery, and stimulate higher-order thinking skills. Ultimately, the results imply that the practical exercises of the microlearning-based module meet the standards.

Through their ability to promote learning, practical exercises and drills promoted the achievement of learners. For instance, a lesson activity that was well-constructed provided a learner with new insights, and a worksheet that was appealing gave the student new opportunities to practice a new skill that they acquired in class (The Open University UK, 2024). In addition to providing repetition, these exercises proved beneficial to the learning process since they allowed the learner to independently explore many aspects of the knowledge content.

Clarity was Highly Valid (3.87) as to the level of content validity of the developed microlearning-based module in Araling Panlipunan 8. This also revealed that all the indicators were **Highly Valid**. Consequently, the indicators “Language use is clear and easy to understand” and “The concepts for each activity are re-arranged logically and ensure that there is no duplication” both yielded the highest mean score of **3.93**, whereas the indicators “Information is clear and simple” and “Information suits learners' interest” both received the lowest mean score of **3.87**. The standard deviation of **0.28** indicates minimal variability in the evaluators' responses, suggesting a strong consensus regarding the clarity of the module's content.

Almarode et al. (2025) also emphasized that clarity facilitated learners in directing their educational pursuits. When students comprehended expectations, they exhibited enhanced self-efficacy and agency in their learning. This confidence resulted in a heightened readiness to undertake intellectual risks and endure adversities. With clarity regarding the learning objectives, learners could more effectively assess their current level of comprehension, make informed decisions about their subsequent learning paths, and track their educational progress. Ultimately, autonomous learners possessed a repertoire of learning strategies and discerned the appropriate moments to implement them, aligning with the specific context within their educational advancement.

In the same light, when faculty capitalized on organization and clarity and developed well-structured courses, articulated syllabi and assignment guidelines in comprehensible language, and elucidated course material effectively, students perceived these actions as signs of faculty commitment to their academic success and dedication to effective teaching (New York Institute of Technology, 2024). This perception fostered a positive learning environment where students became more engaged in their studies and demonstrated greater motivation to excel academically. Consequently, they adopted more effective study habits and enhanced their learning efforts, leading to improved educational outcomes and a stronger sense of academic responsibility.

Usefulness was **Very Acceptable (3.77)** as to the level of acceptability of the developed microlearning-based module in *Araling Panlipunan 8*. The data also revealed that all the indicators were also **Very Acceptable**. In this manner, the indicators, “*The concepts in the material were simple and comprehensible*” and “*The material helped the students master the topics at their own pace*” both yielded the highest mean score of **3.87** while the indicator, “*The materials prepared the learners to think logically and critically*” received the lowest mean score of **3.53**. The standard deviation of **0.35** suggested a moderate level of variability in the evaluators' responses, had slight differences in individual assessments. This variability reflected diverse perspectives on the module's usefulness, with some evaluators perceived it as highly effective in supporting independent learning, while others may have noted areas for improvement in fostering critical thinking skills.

Likewise, the results pointed out that the developed microlearning-based module is very useful as it prepared learners for critical thinking, was simple and comprehensible, helped students master the topics independently, provided development opportunities, offered adequate information, motivated learners to be actively involved, stimulated their intellect, and sought interrelations between and across topics. Ultimately, the results implied that the usefulness of the microlearning-based module meets the standards.

Similarly, according to Cramer et al. (2020), it was deemed useful when it possessed explicit objectives and outcomes that delineated learner expectations upon completion. It included engaging activities that encompassed a variety of interactive elements, such as discussions, exercises, simulations, or projects. Pertinent resources offered access to an array of readings, videos, links, or other materials that reinforced the learning objectives. Assessment methods utilized diverse evaluation techniques to measure learners' comprehension and advancement, including quizzes, assignments, or presentations. A coherent structure and organization ensured clear sections and a seamless progression of content.

Presentation was **Very Acceptable (3.85)** as to the level of acceptability of the developed microlearning-based module in *Araling Panlipunan 8*. The data also revealed that all the indicators are also **Very Acceptable**. Consequently, the indicator, “*The topics fit the learners' needs*” yielded the highest mean score of **3.93**, whereas the indicators, “*Topics are presented in logical and sequential order*” and “*The direction is concise readable, and easy to follow.*” both received the lowest mean score of **3.80**. The standard deviation of **0.30** suggests a moderate level of variability in the evaluators' responses, had a slight differences in individual assessments. This variability reflects diverse perspectives on the module's presentation, with some evaluators perceiving it as highly effective in structuring content logically, while others may have noted minor areas for improvement in sequencing and clarity.

Accordingly, the results indicate that the developed microlearning-based module manifests logically and sequentially ordered topics, ensuring a smooth and coherent flow of information that enhances comprehension and engagement. The module features a concise and readable direction, allowing learners to navigate instructional content effortlessly and focus on key concepts without confusion. Additionally, the topics are well-fitted to the learners' needs, aligning with educational objectives and ensuring relevance to their cognitive development and academic requirements. The lesson presentation is both

interesting and attractive, utilizing engaging visuals, structured formatting, and interactive elements that foster student motivation and active participation.

Bril (2021) stated that presentations in educational modules were essential for engaging learners, promoting active involvement, and augmenting comprehension through varied communication methods and interactive components, ultimately resulting in enhanced learning outcomes. The presentation enhanced learning by integrating images, audio, and multimedia elements, thereby engaging learners and facilitating the comprehension of complicated subjects. It promoted active engagement via debates, question-and-answer sessions, and group activities, cultivating a more collaborative and stimulating educational atmosphere.

Suitability was **Very Acceptable (3.76)** as to the level of acceptability of the developed microlearning-based module in *Araling Panlipunan 8.*. The data also revealed that all the indicators are also **Very Acceptable**. In this manner, the indicator, “*Language of the program is within the vocabulary range of learners*” yielded the highest mean score of **3.87** while the indicator, “*Enrichment activities cater the different learning needs of learners*” received the lowest mean score of **3.67**. The standard deviation of **0.39** suggests a moderate level of variability in the evaluators' responses, had some differences in individual assessments. This variability reflects diverse perspectives on the module's suitability, with some evaluators perceiving it as highly effective in addressing learners' vocabulary range, while others may have noted areas for improvement in enrichment activities.

Likewise, the results point out that the developed microlearning-based module is highly suitable, as its activities consider a variety of learner capabilities, ensuring inclusivity and accessibility for different learning levels. The module aligns with the subject matter, maintaining relevance and appropriateness to academic standards and curriculum requirements. Additionally, the activities are engaging, interesting, and motivating, fostering active participation and encouraging deeper exploration of the topics presented. The module effectively caters to the diverse needs of learners, providing structured yet flexible materials that support independent learning. Furthermore, the language used throughout the module is within the vocabulary range of students, ensuring clarity and comprehension without unnecessary complexity.

In addition, Dopson (2024) supported this by emphasizing that the suitability of a learning module demonstrated involvement and diversity. The content integrated interactive components such as quizzes, simulations, and discussions to promote active learning and engagement; employed diverse formats (text, images, videos, audio) to accommodate various learning styles and preferences; and related the material to real-world examples and applications to enhance its significance and relevance. Additionally, it possessed structure and organization, presented information in a logical and coherent sequence that built upon existing knowledge and skills; employed a clear and predictable framework to assist learners in navigating the module and maintaining focus, while deconstructing complex subjects into smaller, manageable units to improve retention and comprehension.

Research Objective 3. Determine the pretest and posttest results of the Grade 8 students upon utilizing the Developed Microlearning-based Module in *Araling Panlipunan 8*.

In terms of the pretest, the student participants received an average score of **72.50**, which was verbally interpreted as **Did Not Meet Expectations** based on the Department of Education's standards. Among the participants, only 1 student (2.5%) achieved a Very Satisfactory rating, demonstrating a strong grasp of the assessed material. Meanwhile, 9 students (22.5%) attained a Satisfactory rating, indicating an acceptable but limited understanding of the topics covered. Additionally, 8 students (20.0%) fell under the Fairly Satisfactory category, meaning they exhibited partial comprehension but struggled with key concepts. The largest portion of the group, 22 students (55%), did not meet the expectations set for the assessment, reflecting a considerable gap in knowledge and mastery. The standard deviation of 7.94 indicates a high level of variability in the pretest scores, suggesting that student performance varied significantly across different competency levels. A substantial portion struggled to meet the expected standards, leading to a wide dispersion in scores.

These results suggest that a significant number of students face challenges in grasping the required competencies, underscoring the importance of targeted instructional interventions, reinforcement activities, and supplementary learning materials to enhance their understanding and performance in subsequent assessments. The need for personalized support mechanisms, such as differentiated instruction, remedial sessions, and adaptive learning strategies, is to address the specific areas where students struggle. Additionally, integrating interactive and engaging learning materials, such as video-based microlearning modules and real-world applications, can provide students with accessible and relatable content that reinforces key concepts.

Chai (2023) also found that without proper consideration of innovative teaching strategies, poor knowledge of current issues, history, and economics led to weak social studies competencies, which contributed to the subpar academic performance and achievement of Filipino students. Hence, taking into account learners' attention span and cognitive load became a method to address the persistent educational challenges affecting the entire sector, particularly in their knowledge of Social Studies. This subject remained one of the most crucial facets of academic learning as it explored the practical realities of society and the world in which students lived.

In terms of the posttest, the student respondents got an average of **87.95**, which was verbally interpreted as **Very Satisfactory**. There were 21 (52.5%) student participants who got Outstanding, 9 (22.5%) Very Satisfactory, 5 (12.5%) Satisfactory, 4 (10%) Fairly Satisfactory, and 1 (2.5%) who Did not Meet Expectations. The results showed that the student participants significantly improved their academic performance upon the utilization of the developed Microlearning-based Module in *Araling Panlipunan 8*. The standard deviation of 6.89 indicates a moderate level of variability in the posttest scores, suggesting that while most students performed well, there were still some differences in individual assessments.

The results suggest that the developed Microlearning-based Module in *Araling Panlipunan 8* effectively enhances students' academic performance. A significant number

of participants demonstrate substantial improvement, reaching higher levels of achievement compared to their initial assessment. Many students excel, while a few still require additional support, highlighting the need for continuous instructional refinement. This outcome reinforces the module's ability to support learning by providing engaging and well-structured content that helps students grasp key concepts more effectively. The differences in scores indicate varying levels of understanding, suggesting that while most students benefit greatly, individual learning styles and comprehension rates continue to influence performance variation.

The aforementioned results were anchored in the findings of Leong et al. (2020), who elucidated that microlearning is an efficacious approach for enhancing students' retention of information. This instructional method delivers short, focused learning units that enable learners to engage with key concepts efficiently while minimizing cognitive overload. By structuring content into concise and digestible segments, learners demonstrate improved comprehension, recall, and application of knowledge. Moreover, microlearning fosters active engagement, as it encourages learners to process information swiftly while concentrating on essential details. Such an approach aligns with contemporary educational strategies, thereby maximizing the effectiveness of learning interventions and accommodating diverse learning preferences.

There was a significant difference between the pretest and posttest results of the Grade 8 students on the utilization of the developed Microlearning-based Module in *Araling Panlipunan 8*. This yielded a probability value is .000, which was less than the level of significance at .05. This denotes that the null hypothesis was rejected.

This implies that the developed Microlearning-based Module in *Araling Panlipunan 8* has a meaningful impact on student learning and academic performance. The noticeable improvement from the pretest to the posttest demonstrates that the module effectively enhances comprehension and mastery of the subject matter. Since the analysis confirms a significant difference in students' scores, this suggests that the module supports knowledge retention, strengthens critical thinking, and facilitates independent learning. The findings further validate the effectiveness of microlearning as an instructional approach, proving that it helps students grasp key concepts more efficiently within a structured learning framework.

This result was supported by Andriotis (2022), who argued that a crucial trait of all microlearning-based educational initiatives was their emphasis on concise content delivery. These alternatives consisted of either succinct educational modules or brief instructional exercises. Microlearning provided learners with succinct and easily accessible material that could be studied at their own pace and leisure. Content existed in several formats, ranging from text to highly interactive multimedia; nonetheless, it remained imperative that it was concise. Thus, microlearning emerged as a learning method characterized by increased engagement, decreased time commitment, and lower production costs compared to traditional learning methods. Although not universally applicable, this method demonstrated significant efficacy in corporate, commercial, and educational training environments.

Conclusions

The development and validation of the microlearning-based module titled '*MAPA: Microlearning Agapay sa Pagkatuto sa Araling Panlipunan 8*' successfully addressed the educational challenges faced by Grade 8 learners in San Cristobal National High School, particularly their low performance in World History. Anchored on the principles of Microlearning Theory, Information Processing Theory, and Cognitive Load Theory, the module was systematically crafted using the ADDIE model to meet the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) outlined by the Department of Education.

In terms of **content validity**, the module received a perfect Content Validity Index (CVI) of 1.00 and was rated Highly Valid across all indicators: objectives, directions, topics, practical exercises, and clarity. Additionally, expert Social Studies teachers rated its **acceptability** as Very Acceptable based on usefulness, presentation, and suitability. This shows the module's relevance and practical use in real classroom settings

The **educational impact** of the module was evident in the significant improvement in students' academic performance. The pretest average of 72.50 (Did Not Meet Expectations) rose to a posttest average of 87.95 (Very Satisfactory). A paired t-test confirmed a statistically significant difference ($t = -15.873$, $p < 0.05$). This demonstrated the module's effectiveness in improving comprehension and retention through clear, engaging, and focused learning segments.

The **assessment strategies** included in the module—pretest and posttest evaluations, performance tasks, and reflective activities—validated its success in addressing learners' short attention spans and in strengthening foundational knowledge in Araling Panlipunan 8. These assessments matched well with the IDEA (Introduction, Development, Engagement, Assimilation) model, ensuring a smooth flow in learning.

Finally, **feedback from teachers and stakeholders** was overwhelmingly positive. Teachers recognized the module's potential to improve instructional delivery, particularly in a subject like Araling Panlipunan that often struggled with innovation. Stakeholders, including school administrators and parents, acknowledged its practicality, adapted it to modular and blended learning, and noted its alignment with learners' digital habits.

Overall, the research showed that microlearning-based instruction provided an effective and innovative way to deliver essential learning skills in Araling Panlipunan 8. The module acted not only as a tool for content delivery but also as a solution to current educational challenges such as student disengagement, content overload, and digital distractions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are proposed:

For Teachers and Instructional Designers

Educators are encouraged to adopt microlearning-based instructional strategies in Social Studies and other subjects. The I.D.E.A. format can be used as a flexible framework for designing modular lessons that improve comprehension, attention, and

learner engagement.

For School Administrators and Curriculum Planners

Schools and curriculum developers are advised to consider the integration of microlearning modules into their regular instructional plans, particularly for subjects that are content-heavy or commonly neglected in modular learning. Institutionalizing microlearning-based modules can help ensure equitable and effective delivery of key competencies.

For the Department of Education (DepEd)

The DepEd may consider endorsing the use of microlearning-based instructional materials as supplemental tools in both classroom and blended learning environments. This aligns with the goals of the Basic Education Development Plan (BEDP) 2030 and addresses learner diversity and adaptability.

For Future Researchers

Future studies may expand on this work by exploring the long-term effects of microlearning on knowledge retention, its application to other subjects and grade levels, and its impact on student motivation. Qualitative investigations on learner experiences and feedback may further enhance the design of future modules.

By implementing these recommendations, the adoption of microlearning in the Philippine education system can be expanded, ultimately improving student achievement, engagement, and instructional effectiveness in Araling Panlipunan and beyond.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adhered to ethical standards set by the Laguna College of Business and Arts Thesis Writing Manual and the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Respondents provided informed consent, ensuring voluntary participation without coercion. All data were anonymized to protect privacy and confidentiality. Lastly, the utility of Canva platforms has also been helpful and considered in this research.

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